

Bulk Analysis of Soils by Fast Neutron Activation Analysis using ^{241}Am -Be Neutron Source

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Neutron activation analysis methods based on fast neutron irradiation using ^{241}Am -Be neutron source have been suggested for the determination of Al, Fe and Si in soils. The methods induce reactions $^{27}\text{Al}(n,p)^{27}\text{Mg}$, $^{56}\text{Fe}(n,p)^{56}\text{Mn}$ and $^{28}\text{Si}(n,p)^{28}\text{Al}$ and the resultant activities of 0.844, 0.847 and 1.78 MeV γ -rays emitted from the product radionuclides respectively are counted on $3'' \times 3''$ NaI(Tl) detector coupled with a single channel pulse height analyser. The results are in good agreement with wet chemical methods. The methods are fast, non-destructive and economic.

SOILS in general, have silicate matrix similar to terrestrial rocks but not so distinct in elemental composition. Mostly they represent a homogeneous or heterogeneous mixtures of different types of rocks from nearby areas. Analysis of soils may be helpful in geological mapping, to agriculture scientists and to construction engineers. It may also be used in nuclear industry for studying soil characteristics before constructing a nuclear reactor or even for the disposal of radioactive waste.

Wet chemical or instrumental methods require fusion dissolution followed by sophisticated chemical separation schemes which are often tedious and time consuming. Several nuclear methods have been developed for the analysis of soils^{1,2}. Neutron activation analysis (NAA) is one of the most suitable methods for the determination of majority of elements in different matrices³. Recently, low flux isotopic sources have gained much importance in bulk analysis^{4,5}, process control⁶ and mineralogical processes⁶. A neutron activation method has been suggested for measuring the water content in soils⁷. A thermal neutron irradiation method has been reported for the determination of Al in soils and plants⁸. Silicon and iron, important constituents of all soils⁹ have also been determined in soils^{10,11}. Importance of NAA of soils may be realised from the fact that IAEA has come up with a Certified Reference Material, Soil-5 used as comparator¹². In continuation of our work on the determination of Al, Fe and Si in bauxites and other geological ores¹³⁻¹⁵, we report here our results on the bulk analysis of these elements in soils using fast neutrons from a 5 Ci ^{241}Am -Be source. Such sources have been extensively used for the analysis of various elements using thermal and fast neutrons (4-6 Mev)¹⁶⁻¹⁸.

Experimental

Sample preparation and counting: Six different soil samples, black, red (murum), yellow, sand,

multani and red geru, and two local basalt samples were analysed. The samples were collected locally e.g. black soil from nearby garden, sand used for mixing with cement and is likely to be from Kanhan river bed and red coloured murum vastly found in this region was picked up from road side. Other three varieties of soils, i.e. yellow (often called Pilli Mitti), multani (used to wash scalp hair by ladies) and red geru were purchased from the local market. Two basalt samples were collected from Ambazari and Takali areas in Nagpur. The samples were powdered and dried overnight at 90°. USGS rock BCR-1 and IAEA standard Soil-5 were used as comparators. Each samples (~1 g) of soils, basalts and standards were packed in polythene bags (3 cm $\times$ 1cm). The samples and the standards were irradiated in a 5 curie ^{241}Am -Be source in 0.5 mm thick Cd tray to cut off thermal neutrons¹⁹. The details of experimental parameters and nuclear characteristics^{19,20}, are given in Table 1. The activity of irradiated samples was counted at the photopeak position on a $3'' \times 3''$ NaI (Tl) detector (Bicron, U.S.A.) coupled with single channel pulse height analyser (ECIL, Hyderabad). Since half-life of ^{28}Al is short (2.3 min) a cyclic activation analysis procedure was employed for Si^{14,15}. About 1000 or more counts were collected in each case and at least three replicate analyses were performed. Identification of nuclides was done by characteristic γ -ray spectra and half-life measurement in all the cases.

Chemical methods: Some of the soil samples were also analysed by standard chemical methods, viz. gravimetry and spectrophotometry for all the three elements. The results given in Table 2 are in satisfactory agreement.

Interferences: There is a possibility of several nuclear interferences due to production of radionuclides from other nuclear reactions or γ -ray energies being emitted by other nuclides which may be formed. These are listed in Table 1. Also

BCR-1 and Soil-5 were also determined using each other as a standard and other USGS standards¹⁴, like AGV-1, W-1, DTS-1, GSP-1. Abundances of Si in standards was also checked using extrapure SiO₂ as a primary standard. The results of Al, Si and Fe in different soils and basalts alongwith BCR-1 and Soil-5 are given in Table 2. The calculated values in BCR-1 and Soil-5 are in excellent agreement with the literature values. Therefore, we can say that the values of Al, Fe and Si in various types of soils and basalts are reliable. For some of the soils, wet chemical analysis (gravimetry and spectrophotometry) was performed and the results were in good agreement with those of the NAA results^{10,11}. For each sample three replicate analyses using different weights were performed and the mean values alongwith standard deviations are reported in Table 2. The standard deviations for all the three elements are $\leq 0.5\%$ in most cases. The standard deviations of single determination based on counting statistics are 1.0, 2.5 and 1.5% for Al, Fe and Si, respectively.

A correlation of Fe vs Si abundances in various soils is presented in Fig. 1, showing somewhat

Fig. 1. Fe and Si abundances in various types of soil samples.

inverse linear relationship. It seems that abundances of Fe and Si are inversely related. It is to be noted that this correlation is more or less very approximate because the points for geru and the two basalts which are not soils in true sense are quite off the line. Such plots are quite frequently used by geochemists for characterisation of different types of terrestrial rocks¹⁵ and lunar soils¹⁶. Eventhough large number of analyses are required in such cases but our plot does indicate that points for basaltic rocks are off the line. Similarly

geru is also not the natural soil but a recrystallised form.

A comparative study of the three elements in different soils indicates that aluminium content varies in the range 4–8%. The Si content is highest in yellow soil and sand and lowest in red soil or murum and geru. Similarly, iron is lowest in yellow soil and highest in red soil. On the other hand, black soil, a characteristic of this region and commonly used in gardens, has medium range of Si (24.29%) and Fe (7.13%) content.

Thus, low flux isotopic neutron sources have great potential for the determination of Al, Fe and Si in soils. The methods could be easily employed in any soil survey laboratory. The methods are simple, fast, economic, non-destructive and yield reliable data.

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